

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CLINICAL AND MICROBIOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF ACUTE TONSILLITIS IN CHILDREN AND ADULTS

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Abstract

Acute tonsillitis is one of the most common infectious diseases of the upper respiratory tract, characterized by inflammatory lesions of the palatine tonsils and significant variability of clinical manifestations. Despite the traditional view of the leading role of bacterial pathogens, modern studies indicate a significant role for viral agents and opportunistic microbiota. The aim of this study was to examine the microbiological composition of palatine tonsils in patients with acute tonsillitis across different age groups and to identify possible etiological factors of the disease.

The study involved 45 people, including 30 patients with acute tonsillitis and 15 healthy control patients. A bacteriological study of smears from the palatine tonsils was performed, followed by identification of the microorganisms. It was found that in most cases, opportunistic microflora prevails, while the frequency of detection of classical bacterial pathogens remains low.

The results confirm the significant role of viral etiology in the development of acute tonsillitis and justify the need to rationalize antibacterial therapy based on microbiological data.

Keywords: acute tonsillitis, microbiota, viral infection, *Streptococcus pyogenes*, antibiotic resistance.

Introduction

Acute tonsillitis occupies a leading position among infectious diseases of the upper respiratory tract and is a frequent reason for patients to seek medical help. A particularly high incidence is observed among school-age children, which is associated with the immaturity of the immune system and the high intensity of contacts within groups. In adult patients, the disease also occurs frequently and may be accompanied by complications, particularly peritonsillar abscesses or systemic reactions [1].

For a long time, the etiology of acute tonsillitis was considered mainly in terms of bacterial infection, with emphasis on group A β -hemolytic streptococcus (*Streptococcus pyogenes*) [2, 3]. At the same time, modern data indicate that a significant proportion of cases have a viral origin, particularly adenoviruses, influenza viruses, parainfluenza viruses, rhinoviruses, and Epstein-Barr virus. This significantly complicates the differential diagnosis and the selection of optimal therapeutic strategies [4].

A key role in the pathogenesis of the disease is played by the palatine tonsil microbiota. Normally, it is represented by a variety of symbiotic microorganisms that provide colonization resistance. Disruption of this balance can contribute to the development of inflammation even in the absence of classical pathogens [5].

In view of this, it is relevant to study the microbiological features of acute tonsillitis, taking into account age differences, which was the purpose of this study.

The study was prospective and comparative, and involved patients across different age groups. The main group consisted of 30 people with a clinically confirmed diagnosis of acute tonsillitis. It included 18 children aged 5 to 14 and 12 adults aged 20 to 40. The control group consisted of 15 individuals who were practically healthy and without signs of acute respiratory disease.

The inclusion criteria were the presence of typical clinical manifestations of acute tonsillitis (sore throat, tonsil hyperemia, plaques, fever). The exclusion criteria were prior administration of antibacterial drugs within the last 14 days and the presence of chronic diseases during the exacerbation phase.

The biological material was collected with sterile swabs from the palatine tonsil surfaces in the morning, before meals. The obtained samples were immediately transported to the laboratory for further bacteriological examination.

Cultivation was carried out on standard nutrient media, and microorganisms were subsequently identified based on morphological, cultural, and biochemical properties. A quantitative assessment was carried out, accounting for the intensity of colony growth.

Statistical analysis included determination of relative frequencies and mean values, and assessment of the reliability of differences using the χ^2 criterion. The level of statistical significance was accepted at $p < 0.05$.

The analysis revealed that the microbiological spectrum in patients with acute tonsillitis is characterized by significant diversity and heterogeneity. The most common were opportunistic microorganisms, particularly *Streptococcus viridans*, which were detected in 55% of cases. The obtained data indicate the dominance of commensal and opportunistic flora in the palatine tonsil microbiota during the acute inflammatory process.

The frequency of detection of classical bacterial pathogens was significantly lower. Thus, *Streptococcus pyogenes* was identified in only 10% of patients, and *Staphylococcus aureus* in 8%. Comparison of the frequency of detection of opportunistic microbiota and obligate pathogens showed a statistically significant difference ($\chi^2 = 6.12$; $p < 0.05$), which confirms the predominance of non-pathogenic or opportunistic microorganisms in the study group.

In the control group, normal symbiotic microorganisms predominated, accounting for about 70% of

the microbiota. At the same time, pathogenic bacteria were not detected in any case. Comparative analysis between the main and control groups demonstrated statistically significant differences in the frequency of pathogen detection ($\chi^2 = 5.48$; $p < 0.05$), confirming their association with the inflammatory process.

Age analysis showed certain differences in the microbiological spectrum. In children, the detection rate of *Streptococcus pyogenes* was 12%, while in adults, 8%. At the same time, *Staphylococcus aureus* was more often detected in adults (10%) compared to children (6%). However, these differences did not reach statistical significance ($p > 0.05$), which may be due to the limited sample size.

The detection frequency of *Streptococcus viridans* was similar in children (57%) and adults (52%), and no statistically significant differences were observed ($p > 0.05$). This indicates the relative stability of colonization by opportunistic microbiota across age groups.

Thus, the results of statistical analysis confirm that in acute tonsillitis, opportunistic microbiota prevails, while classical bacterial pathogens play a less significant role. The absence of significant age differences indicates the universality of the revealed patterns.

Table 1

Distribution of microorganisms in patients with acute tonsillitis

Microorganism	Children (%)	Adults (%)	Total (%)
<i>Streptococcus viridans</i>	57	52	55
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i>	12	8	10
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	6	10	8
Other bacteria	10	12	11
Normal microbiota	15	18	16

The results indicate the complex, multifactorial nature of acute tonsillitis etiology. The predominance of opportunistic microbiota can be considered a manifestation of dysbiosis arising from a viral infection or a decrease in local immunity.

The low frequency of *Streptococcus pyogenes* detection is consistent with modern studies that show that only a subset of cases of acute tonsillitis are of bacterial origin [6, 7]. This is of fundamental importance for clinical practice, as excessive antibiotic use contributes to the development of antibiotic resistance [8, 9].

An important aspect is also the role of viruses that are not detected by standard bacteriological methods. This necessitates the use of additional diagnostic approaches, such as molecular genetic methods [10, 11].

In addition, the results emphasize the importance of an individualized approach to treatment, accounting for the clinical picture, patient age, and laboratory data.

The study allowed us to establish that, in most cases, acute tonsillitis is associated with the predominance of opportunistic microbiota and a relatively low frequency of detection of classical bacterial pathogens. This confirms the significant role of viral infection in the development of the disease.

Conclusion

The obtained data justify the need to review approaches to the selection of antibacterial therapy and to introduce modern diagnostic methods. A promising direction is the further study of the interaction between the microbiota and the immune system, which may

contribute to the development of new approaches to the prevention and treatment of acute tonsillitis.

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